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Review of the Book, *Technology-Enhanced Teaching and Learning: Leading and Supporting the Transformation on Your Campus* by Barone and Hagner

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Introduction

The book, *Technology-Enhanced Teaching and Learning*, relies on recent research and advanced strategies to describe how to integrate technologies into learning environments in college teaching. This book develops a comprehensive understanding and pedagogical foundation in order to provide instructors with the critical skills needed to apply technology within the college teaching curriculum.

The authors, Barone and Hagner propose some practical strategies for applying information, learning process, teaching strategies, and media in college teaching. Moreover, this book shows how information should inform the use of technology in college teaching. In addition, it provides various scenarios that illustrate specific criteria for selecting appropriate technologies in college teaching. It also provides guidance for developing a class using electronic technology and talks about systematic and technical support infrastructure that are needed to enhance the implementation of technology.

Book Analysis

Barone and Hagner discuss how college teaching reflects change in communities. They emphasize the importance of engaging faculty members in the digital learning society. They describe ways of creative using of technology. They identify the challenges of using technology in learning. This book focuses on the impacts of transitioning from traditional to modern teaching methods on students' achievement. The authors provide some supportive solutions that facilitate the use of technology in a learning environment (Barone & Hagner, 2001).

According to the authors, designing and delivering instructional technology requires team collaboration. The authors provide some responses to intellectual property and legal issues with using technology in college teaching. They discuss in more detail the components of establishing the necessary infrastructure for technology in campuses. This book describes some forms of assessment that have been delivered through technology. One of the important social changes in the last twenty years is the use of technology everywhere. In this new information era, it is crucial to integrate modern technologies into all areas of life including: finance, communication, transportation, and, most definitely, education. The authors discuss in detail the way individuals have become dependent on technologies and related technological resources, such as the internet and databases (Barone & Hagner, 2001; Gaudelli, 2006).

Moreover, Barone and Hagner focus on the multicultural college teaching that emerged in the early 1960s and was conducted as ethnic research. In addition, in the United States and other western countries, multicultural college teaching developed out of social concepts where dialectic issues, violence, and discrimination, were of general public interest. These multicultural discussions have been enhanced by diversity movements. Furthermore, the authors describe some specific organizational issues that are critical for understanding the use of technology (Cushner, 1998; Barone & Hagner, 2001).

This book discusses the improvement of college teaching through increasing the dependency on technology in order to enhance learning environments and students' achievement. Reasons for this modern movement are various, but generally include the necessity to prepare learners for technology-rich and information-based societies. College teaching institutions have integrated instructional devices such as computers, the internet, email, instructional software, information databases, and multimedia design into learning environments. This integration

enhances instructors' abilities to apply the technologies and improve the learning environment in classrooms. One of the important technological implications for preparing instructors over the last twenty years is how to design a suitable learning environment for higher learners (Barone & Hagner, 2001; Gaudelli, 2006).

In addition, Barone and Hagner discuss the technological diversity, which has been increasingly institutionalized in college teaching. Technological diversity has become embedded in all ethnic perspectives, enhancing this orientation to a wider concept of diversity and a more positive system to support social justice. There are several impacts of technological diversity on global and multicultural college teaching systems. There are some important social issues of using integrated technology system in colleges teaching including: affirming culture in pedagogy, social justice, striving for educational equity, and cultural pluralism (Merryfield, 1996, 2002; Barone & Hagner, 2001).

Moreover, their book described the globalization and multicultural college teaching that have shared concepts, similar foci, and general goal combinations. Globalization in college teaching appeared in the 1960s. It is a systematic curriculum designed to enhance postsecondary learners' ability to live in an increasingly problematic and integrated world. Several events illustrate the necessity of a global world community through the 21st century, such as: use and proliferation of weapons of mass destruction, devastating world wars, burgeoning human population growth, and horrific genocides (Barone & Hagner, 2001; Gaudelli, 2003).

Key Considerations of Using Technology and Equity Issues in College Teaching

Barone & Hagner specify the advantages that emerged concerning instructional technology application at the home and at high educational institutions. It raises a large portion of higher learners from diverse ethnic cultures that are regarded at risk of college teaching

system failure. Research on advantaged access and use of instructional technology describes several college students who have been hindered by inequitable usage of instructional technology through the college teaching environment (Barone & Hagner, 2001).

This book describes students from diverse ethnic backgrounds, students living in inner cities, female students, students with disabilities, rural learners, English language learners, and their families. Also, it includes students who are unlikely to graduate or who will leave the college without an adequate level of basic skills (Brown, Hartley, & Higgins, 2001; Barone & Hagner, 2001).

Barone and Hagner discuss several solutions of fixing the inequities in students' computing experiences which may disadvantage learners who still need more technological experience through three methods: their capability to be citizens in the technological community, their efficiency to gain adult employment, and their development of necessary mental skills and highly adequate attitudes towards the college learning environment (Brown, Hartley, & Higgins, 2001).

This book references a study by the U.S. Department of Commerce, which found that white higher learners were two to three times more able to have home access to instructional technology than Hispanic and African American higher learners. The U.S. Department of Commerce found that three to six times more than higher learners from central-city, urban, rural areas, regardless of their basic ethnic culture. Moreover, they reported that in spite of thy being more higher learners in the United States than ever before have used the computers, the distance between those using information technologies has broadened over the past years. The conducted research identifies three hot topics of importance for higher learning educators as they try to imbed the instructional technology into the daily higher learning environment.

The authors explained the basic influences of using technology in college teaching including increasing the usage of technology, proper instruction and integrating the instructional technology. Some barriers and challenges to institutional technology are a lack of multicultural role models, stereotypes held by female higher learners, and lack of adequate instructional structures (Brown, Hartley, & Higgins, 2001; Barone & Hagner, 2001).

Criteria for Effective College Teaching with Technology

Obviously, Barone and Hagner illustrated the idea that no generation is more efficient with internet and communication technologies than today's digital native learners. The digital native learners have grown up in a technological society. Where a paper and pen may have formed the tool of prior decades, today's learners enter the learning environment supported with laptops, smart phones, and ipads. There are many benefits of using these devices in college teaching phases. There are many advantages for these modern instructional movements for instructors in college teaching.

This book specifies many advantages to having a flexibility delivering of learning delivered by technology. It discusses the impact on minimizing the states' financial aid for higher learners' achievement. Instructional technology is enhancing several models of teaching, developing curricula, and spawning rich forms of online research and cooperation. Technology enabled a systematic economy, as many colleges find themselves confronting new challenges. Moreover, it is important to provide students and instructors with the high quality of skills and basic knowledge that are required for efficient dealing with technology in the learning process (Barone & Hagner, 2001; Economist Intelligence Unit, 2008).

Moreover, Barone and Hagner discuss the application of technology in college teaching that tends to develop the college teaching system over what it is supposed to be without

integrated technology. It is not easy to implement technology as instructional materials.

Instructors at the college teaching level can use the information on the class's website, which allows college students to study and achieve the study concepts easily at the location they chose.

This will spark college learners' motivation towards learning. Integrated technology-based instruction directly supports feedback to higher learners and provides correct responses.

In addition, this book introduces the technology as patient and not pre judgmental, which can provide the learners' motivation to enhance the learning process. Concentrated participation and learning devices used for the long distance college learning process and are accessible to the distance learners. The authors argue that the integrated technology in college teaching system prepares learners' to use specific software and make their visual and written projects, which can maintain the high quality of their works (Barone & Hagner, 2001, Bates & Poole, 2003; Dick, W., Carey, L., & Carey, J. O., 2009).

Barone and Hagner discuss that over the next decade, advanced technologies would facilitate higher learning around the globe, and will provide more opportunities for specialization in college teaching methodologies and curriculum than ever before. Through these great opportunities and benefits, emerge challenges and barriers (Barone & Hagner, 2001).

Barriers of Using Technology in College Teaching

Although this book describes many opportunities and benefits of the instructional technology in the college teaching system, there are also several weaknesses. Some of these weaknesses are a lack of high quality training, the large amount of time of implementing technology, and limited access to sufficient quantities of applied technology. To comprehend integrate technology in college teaching process; one must deeply navigate through theories in human behavior as behaviors are influenced by modern technology.

In addition, media psychology is the study of media effects and technological reflections on adult learners, audiences, and communities. Media technology is an increasing aspect influenced by rapidly applying technology in the college teaching system (Hartman, 2002; Barone & Hagner, 2001).

Critiques of this Book, Effects of Technology in College Teaching

There are some specific critiques of this book depending on the previous argumentations. This book does not talk about the new mission and commercial purpose, or special high quality training. It does not explain the effects of achieve effective technology integration in the college teaching environment. Moreover, this book needs to introduce better discussion through further analysis in some particular cases. Each of the good-practice institutions cannot be a perfect example of using effective technology in college teaching. In addition, the discussion of some of the weaknesses and strengths of technology may support the authors' perspective of what fundamentals and infrastructures are necessary.

Another drawback emerges when this book claimed that educators apply technology into education, especially when the quantity of a resource is limited. This often happens because the limited quantity of devices or digital equipment in the learning environment. The authors didn't mention that the use of technology is not enough to maintain the needs of all adult learners. In addition, Barone and Hagner miss the discussion of the unsuitable resource situations of college teaching environments, such as the need to move the learners to an equipment lab instead of having computer access in every learning environment.

Nevertheless, this book needs to give more focus on technology, not as the last goal of the educational process, but as it can be applied to achieve the specified educational goals and objectives. This book should recommend instructors to have strong and high abilities to deal

with technology. Moreover, it needs to explain the advantages over more traditional methods. The authors need to encourage teachers to have the necessary skills and capabilities.

Although there are several limitations, this book by Barone and Hagner was written at a suitable level that could be understood by readers from most academic fields. The authors' method of presenting information is coherent and logically consistent. It leads to clear comprehension and information retention of the concept throughout their book. Moreover, Barone and Hagner organize their discussion logically. In each chapter they provide reform concepts that are necessary for understanding new ideas that needs more clarification.

Further Recommendations

This book should have new information resources and explain how it could be designed and improved whenever the technological infrastructure has been changed. The authors should provide satisfactory quality of discussion, focusing on specific technological devices. This discussion needs to help redesign the higher learning environment that is necessary to achieve learning objectives after such changes. Even after they provide enough explanation of quantity of equipments and instructors, they must illustrate how teachers could adjust the instructional system with available resources.

Moreover, the authors should introduce experimental evidence. This evidence should suggest and discuss the effectiveness of teaching with technology in colleges. They need to focus on the idea that college students learn more in less time and enjoy classes more when receiving instruction enhanced by technology. In addition, the authors should encourage teachers to develop their students' positive attitudes towards learning with new technology. Barone and Hagner need to discuss in more detail the new education system within a technological learning environment.

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